

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Bashardost, Zabehullah, and Ahmadi, Jawida. (2019), The Main Challenges of Public Management in Afghanistan and the Possible Solutions. In: *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, Vol.2, No.4, 865-875.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.02.04.125

The online version of this article can be found at:

<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:

The Asian Institute of Research

The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Social and Political Sciences* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of Social and Political Sciences, which include, but not limited to, Anthropology, Government Studies, Political Sciences, Sociology, International Relations, Public Administration, History, Philosophy, Arts, Education, Linguistics, and Cultural Studies. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of Social and Political Sciences.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

The Main Challenges of Public Management in Afghanistan and the Possible Solutions

Assistant professor Zabehullah Bashardost¹, professor Jawida Ahmadi²

¹ Badakhshan University, Afghanistan. Email: zabehullah.sdu@yahoo.com

² Dean of communication and journalism faculty, Kabul University, Afghanistan.
Email:Jawida.ahmadi@gmail.com

Abstract

The public management of a country has a direct relationship with the governance affairs, the components of good and bad in governance have been defined based on developed and undeveloped countries and indicators of governance. Given these components the governance and public management of a country can understand. Afghanistan is a country that has experienced good governance since 2002, after the anarchic and war. In order to study Afghanistan's public management, we need to look closely at governance in Afghanistan in order to identify the extent to which international standards of governance in Afghanistan have been acceptable, and through it, we can identify the challenges of Afghanistan's administration. This paper, which is titled "The Main Challenges of Public Management in Afghanistan and the Possible Solutions," seeks to provide challenges and possible solutions of public management with a comprehensive vision based on global norms and with respect to cultural complexity, historic and traditional. This paper is written in three chapters, the first chapter which discusses good governance with a short manner and recognizes the position of the Afghan government with regard to the indicators of good governance, the second chapter defines the challenges of the Afghan management, the third chapter addresses the possible solution and ends with a conclusion. The purpose of writing this paper is to identify precisely the components that have had a profound negative impact on the Afghan public management and to prevent the increasing of these challenges proposes the solutions ways. This paper, based on library research, has gained to the authoritative sources that contain the principles of global management and the real challenges facing Afghanistan.

Keywords: Indicators of Good Governance, Public Management of Afghanistan, Main Challenges, Possible Solutions

Introduction

The paper is titled "the main challenges of public management and possible solutions in Afghanistan" defined the good governance and public management based on global indicators, especially in non-developed countries, and tried to find the main challenges and possible solutions of public management of Afghanistan based on those indicators.

Global indicators of good governance help the researcher to define the main challenges of public management. In this paper, the rule of law, transparency, capacity building, high standard of living, solidarity, and reforms have known as indicators of good government in non-developed countries, based on these indicators, Afghanistan has faced to the following challenges in its public administration, such as poverty and unemployment, insecurity and immigration and violation of human right, administration corruption, the negatives role of media, the increasing of threat and war, lack of rule of law, illiteracy and lack of capacity, lack of administration reform, lack of solidarity and lack of population census, these are administration challenges of Afghanistan based on indicators of good government in non-development countries, and it is a big threat to people's life.

To escape this disastrous situation in the Afghan management and to identify a good governance in Afghanistan, this paper points out and evaluates the possible solutions for the challenges which define in the following: the exit of foreign military forces based on replaces best option, the emergence of a responsible government, getting the mechanism of preventing the threat and war in the country, promote the rule of law, maintaining transparency and accountability, creating the national solidarity and political stability, the equal realization of socio-economic development, attention to the meritocracy, and decentralization of power.

The securing rule of law, extending transparency and administrative reforms, and preventing threat and war are the main solution way and they will provide a high-quality public management and enhance the legitimacy of Afghanistan.

First chapter

1.1. The indicators of Good Governance

In a transformed world today, governments alone will not be able to respond to new needs. This requires new patterns that can use all of the community's capacities in public, private and civil sectors to maximize the production and delivery of public services (Amin 2016:2). And this is not possible, except the global indicators for good governance. Based on most scholars and policymakers, good governance is a fundamental ingredient of sustained economic development. In this section, we discuss, in turn, rules-based indicators of governance, and there are many rules that defined from the side of the scholar as indicators (Kraay:4). Aspects such as rule of law, human rights, political stability, education, economic equality, social trust, political legitimacy, and lack of corruption have been pointed out from the side of some others scholars as essential in order to promote economic growth (Bjorn, Hans Ekbrand 2014:8).

But the World Bank emphasizes four dimensions of governance: the capacity and efficiency of the public sector, accountability, legal framework for development, and transparency and information (Rosario G 1999:6). In another perspective the origins of good governance can mostly be traced in societies enjoying a democratic background and tradition, good governance in these kinds of societies and countries were built as a sequence of expanding democratic political parties, transparent elections, independent judiciary systems that observed the rule of law and extension of citizenry values true education and civil movements. But in some countries where are, non-developed countries provide examples of the absence of good governance. In Bulgaria, for instance, nondevelopment, lack of democratic experience, and consequently lack of democratic infrastructure to perform good governance have confronted the country with plenty of problems.

Accordingly, the status of good governance in Afghanistan is more similar to the situation in Bulgaria than in any of the Western European or some others developed countries: good governance and other related concepts such as the constitution, rule of law and democracy in Afghanistan is new and the country doesn't enjoy long historical and practical democratic and good governance experience. The literature of management has described and evaluated the concept of good governance from two perspectives:

1. The general perspective, which doesn't restrict the concept only to the government, but also includes the private sector, civil society, and the systems and mechanism which affect the management, planning, and governance.
2. The specific perspective, which focuses on government. From this perspective, good governance means the transparent execution of duties and responsibilities by a government within the framework of existing laws and principles. I will mostly evaluate the good governance in Afghanistan from the specific perspective and focus on the Afghan government, its possibilities and problems of performing good governance.

By choosing the 'special perspective,' in this paper, I offer sixth concepts, namely: the rule of law, transparency, capacity building, high standard of living, solidarity, and reforms as the major indicators of good governance. Actually, these indicators provide the framework for this paper. The reason I select these sixth indicators comes out of my understanding of Afghanistan's socioeconomic and politico-cultural realities as a non-developed postwar country.

1.1.1. Rule of Law: in public management literature, the rule of law, in general, means all public duties to be done under the rule of law rather than the rule of man. In other words, it means that under the rule of law, we prevent the rule of man, which in most cases results in authoritarian regimes in which man rules the law and uses it as a personal instrument.

1.1.2. Transparency and Accountability: Financial and administrative corruption is one of the most negative elements affecting good governance: As the level of corruption in government increases, the level of good governance decreases. Corruption has its economic, cultural and institutional effects on good governance. It increases the social gap between rich and poor, culturally weakens the moral values of a society and politically decreases the legitimacy of a government and enhances social distrust.

1.1.3. Capacity Building of Human Resources: in most studies and statistics 'human resources' is recognized as a major index to evaluate the level of development in countries. In those studies, the quality and quantity of expertise and educated population is specified as an independent variable for development. Governments that lack efficient expertise and educated population are not able to properly use the existing resources to implement the government projects and achieve governmental and societal goals (Sayed Nasim2016:4).

1.1.4. High Standard of Living: refers to the level of wealth, comfort, material goods, and necessities available to a certain socioeconomic class in a certain geographic area, usually a country. The standard of living includes factors such as income, quality, and availability of employment, class disparity, poverty rate, gross domestic product, inflation rate, quality and availability of education, etc.

1.1.5. Solidarity: solidarity is unity (as of a group or class) that produces or is based on unities of interests, objectives, standards, and sympathies. It refers to the ties in a society that bind people together as one. (Wikipedia)

1.1.6. Reforms: means to provide and motivate the governmental institutions to conduct their duties effectively and achieve the defined goals. For instance, revitalizing the employment and salary mechanisms based on meritocracy, create new governmental structures and rationalizing governmental institutions to keep the public sector lively. (Sayed Nasim2016:5) In general, reforming the public sector requires the following circumstances:

- Decentralization of decision making
- Improving the employment mechanisms based on meritocracy

1.2. Good Governance in Afghanistan

Afghanistan, before the role of the war and threat, was able to experience a relative government based on the rule of law through consensus and reconciliation between tribal leaders and peoples, so on the new government has established since 2001, (Aarya2014: 7). Therefore, the concept of good governance in Afghanistan is new, and the country lacks a practical background of performing good governance in its contemporary history. As mentioned

before, the concept of good governance for the first time entered into Afghan political literature after the fall of the fifty percent war in the Bonn Conference. (Sayed Nasim 2016:5).

After the Bonn conference, the interim administration, the transitional government, and three presidential elections were formed. Not only, these three elections in Afghanistan have not experienced transferring power from one leader to another leader in the form of global norms, but rather the process of electing more support for traditional groups and power networks in the direction of politics or the distribution of resources and state institutions were based on protection Political focused, therefore, state institutions have formed on the basis of political and group considerations, not on the basis of good governance indicators which I mentioned above, such as the protection of the law, human rights, and so on.

As a result of the third election, the national unity government was created, this election due to the lack of criteria for elections announced without legitimacy, due to widespread fraud and US interference in the election affairs (government in public opinion 2016:12). On the other hand, the Afghan government has achieved relative achievements in these two periods, which has not been so visible in the face of many managerial and governmental challenges, for example, expanding of media in its works area, democracy, and freedom of expression and relative rights for women.

With regard to these electoral challenges and the lack of unity among leaders and many other challenges, the results of two survey in 2014 and 2017 in Afghanistan has shown that Afghans are losing their hopes for the future day by day, (Henry dock& M. Fahim2016:12)

Is Afghanistan going the right way or wrong?

years	2017	2016	2015	2014	2013		2010	2009	2008	2007	2006	2005
People/ percentage		%	%	%			%	%	%	%	%	
Right	32,8	29,3	36,8	35,5	58,2		70	40	54	55	56	77
Wrong	61,2	42,8	31	28,3	21		21	38	24	25	24	6
Fifty-fifty	3	4	6	5	3		5	14	15	17	12	11
No idea	5	3	6	4	2		3	9	7	5	4	6

What are the big challenges in Afghanistan from your idea?

The big challenges of Afghanistan	2010		2016-2017
People / percentage	%		%
Poverty and unemployment	34		19
Insecurity	32		33
Administration corruption	14		10
the lack of reconstruction	8		9
Foreign intervention	2		6
Illiteracy and lack of capability	4		6
Narcotic	2		2
Lack of coordination and solidarity	1		7
Lack of the rule of law and accountability	x		7
No idea	2		1

Based on the annual results of these surveys and based on the World Bank mentioned, "Good governance is synonymous with sound development management (Hashimi 2016:4), There is a big difference in reducing people's expectations about the future as well as in the problems of people in recent years.

Second chapter

2.1. The challenges of Public Management of Afghanistan

After 17 years from the anarchic and war, due to the formation of a transitional, contemporary, and three elected government, Afghanistan is still far from achieving the minimum standards for good governance, this is clearly based on the selected indicators which I mentioned above. Based on the good governance indicators and based on the facts that show Afghanistan in the ranking of corruption countries, the third poorest country in the world, the country with the highest crop of drugs, the most insecure country after Syria, with all these facts the main challenges for public management of Afghanistan can be clear, and these are the following: poverty and unemployment, insecurity and immigration and violation of human right, administration corruption, the negatives role of media, the increasing of western and english schools, lack of rule of law, illiteracy and lack of capacity, lack of administration reform and lack of population census. Why has Afghanistan changed since 1996, especially from 2001 up to now as a corruption, insecure, poorest, and human right violation country, while much assistance was provided to Afghanistan? There are many questions about Afghanistan that will respond to discuss each challenge incomplete form (summary report: 25).

2.1.1. Lack of Rule of Law: Afghanistan, as a non-developed country, suffers from a lack of the rule of law. In Afghanistan, particularly culturally-rooted believes challenge the rule of law: believes that the "victor is the right"; the religious interpretation of law, as well as the traditional, belief that "the status quo is eternally out of our control." The domination of war and commanders that prefer the rule of ethnicity to the rule of law, and a historic lack of law-oriented regimes and experiences has seriously damaged the rule of law in Afghanistan, finally, even the person who has a responsibility in the government has not attended to the rule of law (Sayed Nasim 2016:12).

In a research by "the Afghanistan Freedom House Foundation" has revealed that in all three articles of constitutions nearly two articles have been violated, it has also been shown that over the past 14 years, from 162 articles of the constitution 92 of them have been violated, and most of the Contradictories are the government, opposition group (part of people), irresponsible gunmen and foreigners who are military presence. The Highlights issues that have violated include Non-observance of the election time, the release of prisoners without a court order, the presence of the courts by the irresponsible person, the lack of media attention to national interests, and failure to execute court order against the NATO forces that committed the crime. (Ali Aqa, Mazidi 2016:31-32)

2.1.1.1 The Presences of People with Different Idea: The lack of clarity of the constitution against the activities of idea clerics on opposite of the government has provided a way for dangerous activities. Afghanistan is a religious country, and its people are heavily dependent on long-standing traditions, and traditional culture is more applicable than law in some cases, and that is why the idea clerics have used wrong most of the traditional status of the community, the presence of clerics in the queue of the threats is a sign of the wrong culture of these people, according to the some media in Afghanistan, Seventy percent of clerics inside and outside of Afghanistan do negative propaganda by using idea schools against the government.

2.1.1.2 The Negative Role of Media: The media in Afghanistan has grown dramatically in recent years, and it has made open overview for the Afghan society, so this decade can be considered media advance in Afghanistan, in addition, these media has played a positive role in some sectors, they also have played a negative role, that, it has put a very serious adverse effect on the society and government of Afghanistan. Due to the lack of deterrent laws against the media and the media's open system in Afghanistan, the media did not attention to the public interest of Afghanistan, thus the vast majority of media programs in Afghanistan prioritize the interests of small party groups than national interests of Afghanistan or serve the interests of the countries which has major beneficiaries of

Afghan affairs. Also, the opposite groups have used negatively from this afghan open media system. (Wikipedia: Afghan media system)

2.1.2. Lack of Capacity Building of Human Resources and Illiteracy: Most of the international institutions have considered the level of education, skills, and expertise of a nation as the main factor of development and prosperity. Therefore, I claim that a lack of efficient educated, and skilled in the Afghan public sectors are one of the major challenges for good governance and development (human right 2010:3). According to UNESCO, 11 million people are still illiterate in Afghanistan, and only 34 percent of men and 18 percent of women are literate, according to this statistic, 90% of women and more than 60% of men in rural areas are not adequately educated, this is a shocking issue and a great challenge to the Afghan government. (the summary report:12).

2.1.3. Administration Corruption: Corruption means deviation from legal approaches in administration and generally is a kind of 'illegitimate usage of power' in favor of personal interests. Many factors, including complexity and inefficiency of laws, unaccountable bureaucracy, lack of awareness among the citizens regarding their individual rights, lack of access to governmental information, lack of accountability culture and social irresponsibility regarding good governance can be considered as the reasons of growing corruption in Afghanistan, and Existence of corruption has caused decreased in social prestige and prestige of administrative system. (administration corruption :1)

Based on this definition, the International Center for Private International Law (CIPE) is mentioned: "The corruption in Afghanistan is widely recognized as a key challenge for governance and the rule of law, and it has become a barrier to sustainable economic growth." The United Nations Development Program (UNDP) says that a high level of authority, or lack of competition in Afghanistan, will make systems more vulnerable to corruption. UNDP emphasizes that corruption is fundamentally a result of a lack of good and effective government.

Integrity Watch Afghanistan in 2010 has listed the corruption causes in Afghanistan: 63 percent of Afghans believe that this is due to weak accountability systems, 57 percent say low salaries play a key role in corruption, 49% believe that corruption in large amounts of money in circulation is possible in Afghanistan, and 60% of the people believe that donor countries through their private companies have promoted corruption and money laundering in Afghanistan.

According to Annual Transparency International Report, Afghanistan is known as the third country in the world in terms of corruption. Based on Annual Transparency International Report which has just released about Corruption in Different Countries in 2017, categorized countries in 180 categories, Afghanistan ranked in 177th with 15 points.

In 2016, Afghanistan ranked among the 176 countries with the same score of 15 located 169 ranks, in 2015 is located in 166 ranks from 168 countries, and in 2014 after Sudan, North Korea, and Somalia ranked 172 out of 180 countries. (Akser2017:5&71)

Corruption perception indicators for Afghanistan, 2005-2018

Source/indicator	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010		2016	2017	2018
<u>Transparency International</u> , corruption perception index Afghanistan's rank, out of	117/158	-	172/179	176/180	176/178	-		169/176	177/180	
<u>World bank/worldwide</u> governance indicators	2.0	2.9	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0		-	-	
<u>Asia foundation survey</u> /% of afghans who see corruption as a problem	-	18%	16%	14%	17%	14%		-	10%	11%

2.1.4 Insecurity, Immigration, and Violation of Human Right: According to the Afghan Independent Human Rights Commission which was released in the "war and peace" book, civilian casualties and violence against women and human rights violations have increased in recent years, according to this report, in 2017 more than 16,700 human rights abuses cases were registered in the commission. According to this report, more than 2,800 civilians killed, more than 7,700 injured and 5575 cases of violence against women were registered in the AIHRC in 2017, based on this report, 37 non-trial executions, assassinations, honor killings and field trials, 203 violations of the right to liberty and private security, 82 cases of torture and ill-treatment, 183 violations of the rights of defendants and convicts, 27 cases of violations of the right to freedom of choice in spouses, 59 cases of violation of property rights, a two percent increase in the number of unemployed, were including cases of human rights abuses which was happened only this year.

On the other hand, the AIHRC reported on the increase in displaced Afghans from 1.2 million to 1.5 million, as well as it remembered that 600,000 Afghans in the region countries and 354,000 in the European, American and Australian countries are as a migrant, and mentioned, it is a big problem about escaping human capacity from the country.

2.1.5 Poverty and Unemployment : According to the survey of The Central Statistics Bureau of Afghanistan, and the Institute of Technology (ICON), 54.5% of the population of Afghanistan live below the poverty line, this figure represents an increase of 16.2% since 2012, according to this survey in 2016, the unemployment rate in Afghanistan has increased from 32% to 35%. Based on findings of the recent Central Statistical Bureau survey after 2014 and the established of the National Unity Government, the social crisis in Afghanistan has grown. This report has mentioned, unemployment is one of the outcomes of poverty in Afghanistan, and 35% of young people in Afghanistan suffering from unemployment. According to the ADB report, Afghanistan's economic growth has reached from 2.4 to 2.5 percent between 2016 and 2017 (Akser2017:72) and it stopped to 2,5 in 2018.

The Gross Domestic Product per capita in Afghanistan was last recorded at 618.30 US dollars in 2017. The GDP per Capita in Afghanistan is equivalent to 5 percent of the world's average. GDP per capita in Afghanistan averaged 511.02 USD from 2002 until 2017, reaching an all-time high of 633.70 USD in 2013 and a record low of 364.10 USD in 2004. (Wikipedia)

2.1.6 Lack of Reform: Institutionalization Reforms in structures of government based on the needs are among the good governance indicators. The bureaucracy on the administrative system will form, given the old management system and lack of reform in one country (Hashimi 2016:12). Afghan Institutions did not reform yet, except the education sector, other administration in Afghanistan still suffers from a lack of reform. The issue of the lack of networking in most Afghan administrations is still considered a major challenge, most Afghan administration still uses it from the classic system. (Asker 2017:5)

2.1.7 Lack of Population Census: The exact population statistics of a country are vital for the accommodation of human and economic development programs, and countries try to census its population every five or ten years. But in Afghanistan, over the past three decades, there has been no precise and comprehensive census of population, and there are various statistics available. According to Central Statistics, nearly 31 million people live in Afghanistan, while this number is considered by some institutions as a possible figure.

2.1.8 Lack of Solidarity: Lack of coordination among the three bodies of the state (executive, legislative and judicial) is very dangerous for governance, also this issue is main challenges for peoples of Afghanistan, and they are suffering from the inconsistency, ethnic challenge is a big challenge in Afghanistan and it has driven from a lack of solidarity between ethnic's groups, also it has continued a long time in Afghanistan. In major national processes such as elections, the values for the majority of people of Afghanistan are ethnic and language, not law, (government in public opinion, 8 am news paper2016:3) Law and meritocracy take second place after ethnic values.

Third chapter

3.1. The Possible Solution for Public Management of Afghanistan

When a country has experienced not just months or years but decades of disruption, long-term insecurity and etc., it is unreal to think and act in such problems in a short time. Complex problems need carefully conceived responses (William 2008:7); therefore, Afghanistan needs to focus on all challenges from two perspectives.

3.1.1. External Perspective

The presence of USA Opposite groups in Afghanistan is an effective factor for increasing of challenges in the management of Afghanistan and it has paved the way to excuse of western countries, especially the USA as a struggle against ISIS in Afghanistan, at the result the presence of USA and threatening is a caused that the neighbors of Afghanistan don't trust to Afghanistan.

Therefore, Afghanistan needs to review in his foreign policy and it must pave the way to exit of foreign forces and try to find a good option for replacing of USA aids and preventing of threatening. In this case, Afghanistan has to do: A- find convergence ways with neighbors' countries. B- solve its problem with Pakistan in a peaceful way.

3.1.2 Internal Perspective

Based on all management challenges which I mentioned above, the government of Afghanistan needs to find best and possible solution way in internal affairs, and that is very important for authorities and people of Afghanistan, seventy percent management challenges of Afghanistan find among the peoples, so government needs to focus on seriously, and those are the following:

3.1.2.1 The Contribution of All Groups in Power Based on National Reconciliation: In order to successfully break the "vicious circle to repeated war" national reconciliation has to be established as a political process on the national level, reconciliation with the opposite of Afghan government who are satisfied to join the government and want to accept the constitution of Afghanistan, reconciliation with minorities and others who are not happy from government. This process is very important as a huge picture in the political affairs of Afghanistan. (government in public opinion, 8 am news paper 2016:5)

3.1.2.2 Decentralization of Power :After the long history of armed conflict and instability, the Afghans are in desperate search of a way to govern their country. Many political observers are advocating for strengthening the community's self-governance and building local capacities for sustainable development. The majority of Afghans and scholars argue that a decentralized model of governance, based on consensus, devolution of power to the village, district, and provincial levels, and a significant degree of local autonomy is the most suitable model of governance, which can keep the Afghan nation together. Also, in this model, major responsibilities of the central government can be marginalized, e.g., to draft and ratify budget, centralize justice systems for various crimes by using traditional customs, (Sajid 2012:39) to appoint important officials, enforce local laws and regulations, collect local revenues, etc.

3.1.2.3 Transparency : Corruption is a serious challenge of good governance in Afghanistan. To cope with this challenge, the Afghan government must expand and develop transparency in different levels of administration, and Transparency means revealing any financial information and the mechanisms of budget expenditure on time as well as making them accessible to the public and the media.

3.1.2.4 Improving the Rule of Law in the Country: To enjoy a rule of law government, a country must have democratic and democratically approved laws, the independent judiciary and neutral and lawful police. (Afet 2017:12) To provide a rule of law government, taking the three following steps in Afghanistan is crucial:

- Improving the capacity of the Afghan judiciary
- Improving the coordination of judiciary with other governmental bodies
- Improving the quality of justice

3.1.2.4.1 Struggling Against Threaten: The radical people like commanders become more aggravated in the absence of preventing law and good governance in Afghanistan, leading to a decline in governance, they penetrate to the public opinion every day by using radical ideas mentality and make change peoples idea to negative form. Given this situation, the government must take appropriate measures to prevent this phenomenon, and it will be useful for the government to prevent from this phenomenon by military pressure on radical schools in a short period and design a long-term strategy for making mentality by the scientific institutions.

3.1.2.4.2 The Prevention of Media Propaganda: Regarding the negative points of the media mentioned above, the government is obligated to pass a new law to prevent the publications which are against national interests. While a majority of people of Afghanistan are illiterate, and most of them cannot analyze the political issues, the existence of an open media system is not useful for peoples with the current status of Afghanistan.

3.1.2.5 Accelerating the Reforms: Based on this background and culture, which I mentioned above, the mechanisms of employment and management have been influenced by the ethnic, religious and political leaders who perform as parliamentarians or ministers and prefer political and ethical ties to professionalism. Consequently, the traditional culture of management, which is based on political and identity-based values, dominates the Afghan public sector, which prevents any type of reforms. Eventually, the public sector rules the citizens instead of providing services for the citizens. (Sayed Nasim:13)

Therefore, the Afghan public sector must be reformed. The Afghan government, as its constitutional responsibility, first must establish a sound administration and must be committed to continuous reforms in the future. Administrative reforms in Afghanistan, as it is described in the Afghan National Development Strategy and the Civil Services' Employees Law, must be based on meritocracy and build a sound and accountable administration, which are not affected by political, or identity-based influences. Accordingly, to materialize the administrative reforms described in the Afghanistan constitution and other national documents, the government must take the following steps:

- Employment must be based only on professionalism
- Reforms must be done in different levels of administration
- An observation system must be created, through which the reforms and also the quality of services should be observed.

3.1.2.6 The Equal Realization of Socio-Economic Development: As I noted above, the persistence of lack of balance in development has had a profound impact on vulnerable youths and poor peasants, which are an important part of society, and it has brought the high levels of unemployment and the lack of opportunities, illiteracy, and drug trafficking in Afghanistan. (government in public opinion, 8 am newspaper,2016:3) All Afghan citizens, regardless of ethnic interests, political relations, relations with the government, geographic location, etc., are equal and should benefit from development assistance alike, and the government should pay attention to this issue.

Conclusion

Although the Afghan government has had a little achievement after the fall of the fifty percent war ending, these achievements have not been able to recognize based on the Afghan administration's challenges, and these achievements have covered by challenges in different sectors.

The challenges facing the Afghan administration are due to both internal and external factors:

A. The external factor of these challenges, as I mentioned in the body of this paper, is the presence of NATO, which at the result, has created Challenges such as the internal distrust between the ethnic groups in Afghanistan, concern for neighbors of Afghanistan and administration corruption. B. The internal factors of administration challenges of Afghanistan are as follows:

- The lack of independence in decision-making by Afghan leaders
- Formation of the dangerous idea and lack of a strategy to combat this phenomenon.
- The absence of a clear long-term plan by the government to combat the administration challenges.
- The increasing of ethnic tensions which are a major part of all the challenges in Afghanistan.

In order to eliminate the major factors and challenges of the Afghan government, the government, people and the elites of Afghanistan must accept the following approaches as the first steps:

1. Attention to the regional convergence
2. Get a reasonable solution to the political and Territorial tensions with the neighbor
3. Declaring a general peace within the country based on participating of parties and communities
4. Creating a long-term plan for creating an idea against violence through academic institutions
5. Making a long-term plan for combating administrative challenges such as poverty, corruption, lack of rule of law, etc.
6. The creating a committee for preventing of media propaganda.
7. Neutrality in regional competitions with a clear policy.
8. Commit to building a capable and competent Afghan National Security Force to provide security to its citizens without depending on foreign troops.
9. The Afghans themselves will need to step forward, take the initiative, and bring an end to the culture of aid dependency. The international community cannot do this for them for good.

If the Afghan government with a huge approach can identify the diminutive and hidden angles of security, then with identifying and solving the security challenges will be able to solve all administrative challenges such as poverty and unemployment given the strategic position of Afghanistan, because Afghanistan is located in a macroprojects way, and there are a lot of economic priorities for Afghanistan, if Afghanistan can solve security challenges.

References

- Akser, tabasum. (2017). Afghanistan in 2017 (survey of Afghan people). Kabul: the Asia Foundation,(topic in Persian language)
- Afet. (2014). Afghanistan and Central Asia: prospect and challenges after withdrawal of NATO/ISAF forces. Directorate -general for external policies of the union, European Parliament
- Amin, Abdul Baqi. The way Out of the Afghan Crisis; Criteria, Barriers, and Solutions. Kabul: Center for Strategic and Regional Studies, "topic in the Persian language"
- Aart Kraay, Daniel Kaufmann. Governance Indicators. The World Bank World Bank Institute Global Governance Group and Policy Research Working Paper.
- Administrative Corruption in Afghanistan and its Solutions// www.ncpr.af/download/en/1397208322_1.pdf
- Administration corruption. (2010). Kabul: UNODC// [https://www.unodc.org/...](https://www.unodc.org/)

[/Afghanistan/Afghanistancorruption-survey2010-Eng.pdf](#)

- Berbrich, Henry dock& m Fahim, foruq. (2016). Afghanistan in 2016 (survey of Afghan people). Kabul: the Asia Foundation.
- Bahman, Said Nasim. Good Governance in Afghanistan: Challenges and Solutions. Afghanistan: Balkh University.
- Deve, Afet. (2017). Afghanistan: Challenges and perspectives until2020.the workshop, European Union.
- Governance in public opinion, the results of a poll, (2016). Kabul: 8 am newspaper with Khurshid higher education institute, a topic in the Persian language.
- Hashimi, Sayed hashmatullah. (2016). Civil Service Reform in Afghanistan: Role and Duties of the Civil Service Sector. research for a better of Afghanistan.
- Halleröd, Björn, Hans Ekbrand. (2014). Good Governance – what we think it is and what we really measure. Department of Sociology and Work Science, University of Gothenburg, Sweden.
- Human Rights Dimensions of Poverty in Afghanistan. (2010). Kabul: Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights
- Maley, William. (2008). stabilizing Afghanistan threat and challenges, Asia pacific college diplomacy
- Manasan, Rosario G. Eduardo T. Gonzalez Romualdo B. Gaffud. (1999). Indicators of good government: developing and index of government quality at the LGU level. Discussion paper series NO. 99-04. Mazidi, Ali aqa, Nowruz, Reja. (2016). Constitutional violation at 31 years,” topic in the Persian language”, Kabul: Afghanistan freedom house.
- Nijat, Aarya. (2014). governance in Afghanistan an introduction. Kabul: research for a better of Afghanistan.
- Nojumi, Neamatollah, Dyan Mazurana. (2009). Life and Security in Rural Afghanistan. United States of America, www.rowmanlittlefield.com
- Punyaratabandhu, Suchitra. (2014). Commitment to good governance, development and poverty reduction, Department o f economic & social affairs.
- Sajid, (2012). stable Afghanistan: suggested government model for Afghanistan in post Afghan war scenario, ISSRA Papers
- The summary of analyses reports from the poverty status of Afghanistan. Kabul: the world bank and ministry of economic.
- Tariq, Mohammad Osman. (2010). Afghanistan in 2010(A Survey of the Afghan People). The Asia Foundation.
- Torabi, Yama. (2012). The growing challenge of corruption in Afghanistan. The Asia foundation.
- https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Standard_of_living